

Methodology for the identification of novel ascomycete fungi isolated from *Peltigera* lichens

Karina Moreno¹, **Tomás Miquio**¹, **Yosbany Pérez**^{1,2}, **Nayla Serey**¹, **Katerin Almendras**^{1,2}, **Julieta Orlando**^{1,2}

¹ Laboratorio de Ecología Microbiana, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Chile, Chile

² Instituto Milenio de Biodiversidad de Ecosistemas Antárticos y Subantárticos (BASE), Chile

Description

This protocol outlines the standardized and integrated methodology (molecular and phenotypic) employed at the Microbial Ecology Laboratory, University of Chile, for the rigorous taxonomic identification of potentially novel fungal strains associated with *Peltigera* lichens collected in southern Chile. The core molecular procedure includes DNA extraction, PCR amplification of the ITS and LSU barcoding regions, Sanger sequencing, genetic similarity analysis (BLASTn), and phylogenetic analysis. Complementarily, the protocol describes comprehensive physiological and biochemical characterization assays, including the evaluation of carbon and nitrogen source assimilation, determination of thermal growth profiles, and detailed morphological characterization. This integrated workflow enables the accurate description of new lichenicolous ascomycete taxa, providing a solid foundation for future studies in fungal ecology, systematics, and biotechnology.

The production of this methodology was supported by ANID – Programa Iniciativa Científica Milenio ICN2021_002.

Methodology

Ascomycete isolates

A total of five isolates of ascomycete fungi were identified. These fungi were isolated from *Peltigera* lichens from southern Chile: *P. frigida*, “*P. ponojensis/monticola* 11”, and *P. rufescens* lichens. Previously, Pérez et al. (2023) identified these isolates at the genus level as *Exophiala* (T020-B09, T024-B05), *Phaeococcomyces* (T020-B07) *Lapidomyces* (K045-B04) and *Retiarius* (C023-B40).

Molecular identification

Genomic DNA from each isolate was extracted using the DNeasy PowerSoil Kit (Qiagen, USA) with minor modifications to the manufacturer’s protocol. Fungal cells from pure cultures were resuspended in 800 µL of lysis buffer and vortexed for 30 seconds. The suspension was transferred to bead tubes and subjected to mechanical disruption using a

FastPrep-24™ homogenizer (MP Biomedicals, USA) for 30 seconds at 5 m/s. The remaining purification steps were performed according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Subsequently, the ITS region was amplified using the ITS1F (Gardes and Bruns 1993) and ITS4 primers (White et al. 1990), and the LSU region using the LR0R and LR7 primers (Vilgalys and Hester 1990; De Long et al. 2013). PCR amplifications were conducted in a 25 µl reaction volume, containing 12.5 µl of GoTaq® Green Master Mix (Promega, USA), 0.5 µl of each primer at 10 µM, and 1 µl of yeast DNA, using a Bio-Rad T100 Thermal Cycle (Bio-Rad, USA). The PCR conditions for ITS amplification consisted of an initial denaturation of 5 min at 95 °C, followed by 30 cycles of 45 s at 95 °C, 30 s at 55 °C, 90 s at 72 °C, with a final extension of 10 min at 72 °C. For the amplification of the LSU region, the program included an initial denaturation at 95 °C for 3 min, followed by 40 cycles of 95 °C for 35 s, 47 °C for 1 min, and 72 °C for 2 min, with a final extension at 72 °C for 7 min.

Sanger sequencing was performed by Macrogen (Chile). PCR products were sequenced in the forward direction. The resulting chromatograms were manually edited and cleaned using SnapGene Viewer (<https://www.snapgene.com/snapgeneviewer>) to remove ambiguous bases and low-quality regions. The ITS and LSU sequences were compared with sequences in GenBank using BLASLn (Altschul et al. 1990). We performed the BLAST analysis exclusively against referenced sequences, using the standard database (nr) and fungal type sequences and reference material databases for each marker analyzed. The analysis was optimized for highly similar sequences (megablast), keeping all other parameters constant. Focused on the groups in which our five isolates were placed in the phylogenetic analyses of the first two datasets, additional datasets for each group combining ITS and LSU sequences were performed. In some cases, we assembled ITS datasets to include sequences from isolates for which we could not obtain LSU sequences.

Sequences were aligned using MAFFT version 7 (Kato et al. 2018) with the Q-INS-i algorithm. The resulting alignments were then trimmed to eliminate ambiguously aligned regions. Both pre- and post-trimming checks were performed manually using the alignment viewer and editor AliView v1.27 (Larsson 2014). Gaps at the beginning and end of the alignments were treated as missing data. When applicable, each partition was analyzed individually using the maximum likelihood ultrafast bootstrap in IQTree to assess for potential topological conflicts following Pérez et al. (2024) with modifications. Strongly supported clades (IQTree UF-BS higher than 95%) in disagreement were considered an indication of a significant conflict (Mason-Gamer and Kellogg 1996; Hoang et al. 2018). Since no conflict was detected in our datasets, we combined and analyzed them using maximum likelihood.

Phylogenetic relationships were reconstructed using Maximum Likelihood (ML) on the IQ-TREE web server, with a SH-aLRT test of 1000 replicates and ultrafast bootstrap (UFboot) repetitions (Nguyen et al. 2015), and the substitution model was selected using the Akaike information criterion (AIC) or the corrected Akaike information criterion (AICc) through ModelFinder (Kalyaanamoorthy et al. 2017) implemented in IQ-TREE. Node support was evaluated by standard bootstrap with 1000 pseudo-replicates. A bootstrap percentage $\geq 70\%$ was considered as a phylogenetic support. ML analyses were conducted using the CIPRES

Science Gateway v.3.3 web portal (Miller et al. 2011) and IQ-TREE version 1.6.12 for Windows. Phylogenetic trees were visualized and edited in iTOL v6 (<https://itol.embl.de>).

Biochemical and physiological characterization

For all liquid assays, inocula were prepared from pure cultures in the exponential growth phase. Cell concentration was determined using a Neubauer counting chamber and adjusted to 10^6 – 10^7 cells/mL in sterile distilled water. Aliquots of 100 μ L were used as inoculum for each assay tube (Moreno et al. 2025).

The ability to assimilate different carbon and nitrogen sources was tested following the turbidimetric assay described by Kurtzman et al. (2011). Thirty carbon sources were evaluated, including N-acetyl-D-glucosamine, citric acid, adonitol, D- and L-arabinose, cellobiose, sodium citrate, inulin, ethanol, D-galactose, glycerol, sodium gluconate, D-glucose, D-glucosamine, lactose, maltose, D-mannitol, D-melibiose, D-melicitose, meso-inositol, methanol, myo-inositol, D-raffinose, L-rhamnose, D-ribose, sucrose, D-sorbitol, D-sorbose, D-trehalose, and D-xylose. Tubes containing 4.5 mL of carbon-free basal medium (Yeast Nitrogen Base, Merck 51483) were supplemented with each carbon source at a final concentration of 1%.

Similarly, nitrogen assimilation was assessed using creatine, potassium nitrate, and ammonium sulfate as nitrogen sources. The basal medium (Yeast Carbon Base, Difco™ Y1250) was supplemented with 0.108 g of each nitrogen source. All assays were performed in duplicate, including negative controls lacking the tested substrate. Cultures were incubated in the dark at 15 °C and monitored visually each week for one month; for isolate C023-B40, incubation was extended to two months.

Growth temperature ranges were assessed on Yeast Malt Agar (YMA, 0.3% yeast extract, 0.3% malt extract, 0.5% peptone, 1.0% glucose, 1.5% agar) (Troncoso et al. 2017) (in both agar and liquid form), and for some isolates also on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA, Merck 110,130) at 15 °C and 25 °C. Solid medium plates were incubated at 4, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, and 37 °C. Growth was evaluated weekly for 30 days, except for isolate C023-B40, which was observed for up to seven weeks. Therefore, growth is determined based on the presence of turbidity or mycelium in the medium.

To test the ability to grow in vitamin-free conditions (Y2035-05 Yeast Nitrogen Base (YNB) w/AA & w/AS, Vitamin Free, w/o Dextrose (Powder)), isolates were inoculated into liquid medium formulated as described by Kurtzman et al. (2011) without vitamin supplementation. Growth was monitored at 15 °C by measuring optical density after 30 days. Osmotic tolerance was tested in high-salinity media following the same inoculation procedures. Two media were used: (i) a basal nitrogen medium (Yeast Nitrogen Base, Merck 51483) supplemented with 10% NaCl and 5% glucose, and (ii) slant agar tubes supplemented with 50% glucose and yeast extract (Kurtzman et al. 2011).

Cellular and colony morphology were evaluated following the procedures of Kurtzman et al. (2011). Cultures were grown on YMA medium for five days at 15 °C in darkness before observation.

To observe the cells, an aliquot of the culture was mounted on a microscope slide and examined using a SWIFT light microscope at 40×. Cellular characteristics such as shape, presence of budding, pseudohyphae, or true hyphae were recorded. In addition, to determine cell size, the length and width of 10 cells per isolate were averaged.

To describe the colonies, cultures were observed directly using a NE6745 stereomicroscope (Microimaging, Chile). The length and width of five colonies per isolate were measured, recording the following features: shape, size, elevation, surface, color, texture, and colony margins.

Preservation

All isolates are preserved in glycerol in the Microbial Ecology Laboratory (Pérez et al. 2023) and are metabolically inactive in the Chilean Microbial Resource Collection (<https://www.cchrgm.cl/>). Two isolates are still missing to be included, but they will be sent again shortly.

References

Altschul SF, Gish W, Miller W et al (1990) Basic local alignment search tool. *J Mol Biol* 215:403–410. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-2836\(05\)80360-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-2836(05)80360-2)

De Long JR, Swarts ND, Dixon KW, Egerton-Warburton LM (2013) Mycorrhizal preference promotes habitat invasion by a native Australian orchid: *Microtis media*. *Ann Bot* 111:409–418. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mcs294>

Gardes M, Bruns TD (1993) ITS primers with enhanced specificity for basidiomycetes - application to the identification of mycorrhizae and rusts. *Mol Ecol* 2:113–118. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.1993.tb00005.x>

Hoang DT, Chernomor O, Von Haeseler A et al (2018) UFBoot2: improving the ultrafast bootstrap approximation. *Mol Biol Evol* 35:518–522. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msx281>

Kalyaanamoorthy S, Minh BQ, Wong TKF et al (2017) ModelFinder: fast model selection for accurate phylogenetic estimates. *Nat Methods* 14:587–589. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.4285>

Katoh K, Rozewicki J, Yamada KD (2018) MAFFT online service: multiple sequence alignment, interactive sequence choice and visualization. *Brief Bioinform* 20:1160–1166. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bbx108>

Kurtzman CP, Fell JW, Boekhout T, Robert V (2011) Methods for isolation, phenotypic characterization and maintenance of yeasts. In: Kurtzman C, Fell J, Boekhout T (eds) *The Yeasts* (Fifth Edition). Elsevier Science, pp 87–110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-52149-1.00007-0>

Larsson A (2014) AliView: a fast and lightweight alignment viewer and editor for large datasets. *Bioinformatics* 30:3276–3278. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btu531>

Mason-Gamer RJ, Kellogg EA (1996) Testing for phylogenetic conflict among molecular data sets in the Tribe Triticeae (Gramineae). *Syst Biol* 45:524–545. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sysbio/45.4.524>

Miller MA, Pfeiffer W, Schwartz T (2011) The CIPRES science gateway: a community resource for phylogenetic analyses. In Proceedings of the 2011 TeraGrid conference: extreme digital discovery. New York, USA, pp 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2016741.2016785>

Moreno K, Pérez Y, Miquio-Portell T, Serey N, Soto C, Almendras K, Orlando J (2025) First report of ascomycete fungi of the genera *Exophiala*, *Lapidomyces* and *Retiarius*, associated with Subantarctic lichens of the genus *Peltigera*. X Congreso Latinoamericano de Ciencia Antártica y XII Congreso Chileno de Investigaciones Antárticas. 28 de julio al 1 de agosto 2025. Valdivia, Chile.

Nguyen LT, Schmidt HA, Von Haeseler A, Minh BQ (2015) IQ-TREE: a fast and effective stochastic algorithm for estimating maximum-likelihood phylogenies. *Mol Biol Evol* 32:268–274. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msu300>

Pérez Y, Serey N, Millanes AM, Lizana N, Almendras K, Orlando J (2023) Basidiomycete yeasts isolated from *Peltigera* lichens of southern Chile. *Global Biodiversity Information Facility*. <https://doi.org/10.15468/hw7k9r>

Pérez Y, Almendras K, Millanes AM, Serey N, Yurkov A, Lizana N, Nesci A, Fessia A, Orlando J (2024) *Peltigera* lichens as sources of uncharacterized cultured basidiomycete yeasts. *IMA Fungus*, 15, 39. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43008-024-00170-9>

Troncoso E, Barahona S, Carrasco M et al (2017) Identification and characterization of yeasts isolated from the South Shetland Islands and the Antarctic Peninsula. *Polar Biol* 40:649–658. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00300-016-1988-9>

Vilgalys R, Hester M (1990) Rapid genetic identification and mapping of enzymatically amplified ribosomal DNA from several *Cryptococcus* species. *J Bacteriol* 172:4238–4246. <https://doi.org/10.1128/jb.172.8.4238-4246.1990>

White TJ, Bruns T, Lee S, Taylor J (1990) Amplification and direct sequencing of fungal ribosomal RNA genes for phylogenetics. In: Innis M, Gelfand D, Sninsky J, White J (Eds) *PCR protocols*. Academic Press, 315–322. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-372180-8.50042-1>